

3D-printed micro-optical dark-field condenser

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Optical microscopy is an essential tool in fields such as biology, material science, medicine, and nanotechnology, where resolution and contrast play a crucial role in sample analysis. Dark-field microscopy is fundamental for image contrast and edge enhancement, especially for nearly transparent or nanoscale samples. Dark-field microscopy, however, usually requires a bulky and expensive microscope setup. In this work, we demonstrate a miniaturized, millimeter-sized dark-field condenser fabricated by femtosecond two-photon polymerization 3D-printing. An annular absorbing aperture and a high-numerical aperture lens are combined on a glass substrate. This condenser provides an oblique illumination of the sample, necessary for dark-field imaging. We demonstrate excellent dark-field performance of the 3D-printed dark-field condenser by imaging USAF 1951 resolution test charts and on gold disks with diameters below 500 nm. Our work paves the way for the utilization of miniaturized microscopy techniques that can be rapidly prototyped for applications in medicine or biology. This could possibly lead to entire 3D-printed microscopes with enhanced dark-field imaging capability, for example, for microfluidic chips. Published by Optica Publishing Group under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). Further distribution of this work must maintain attribution to the author(s) and the published article's title, journal citation, and DOI.

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In recent years, two-photon polymerization (2PP) 3D-printing has evolved from fabrication and material optimization [1–5] to the manufacturing of miniature devices such as microfluidics [6] and mechanics [7,8], to optical imaging systems [9–13] and entire optical tools [14–17]. Optical microscopy remains a fundamental tool across the natural sciences, and recent advances in 2PP 3D-printing have facilitated the fabrication of compact, high-numerical aperture optical components for high-resolution imaging [11,12]. To date, 3D-printed optics have been predominantly implemented as imaging systems [9–13,18–22]. 3D printed non-imaging optics include epi-illumination systems [19,23,24], transmission systems [22], and entire optical tools as highlighted above. The implementation of a transmission-

based microscope enables independent optimization of the illumination and detection paths, thereby expanding the range of achievable imaging modalities. By incorporating a light-blocking annular aperture into the illumination path, a dark-field (DF) microscope can be realized. DF microscopy is a well-established technique in optical imaging [25,26], particularly suited for the observation of weakly scattering samples at the micro- and nanoscale [27–31] or transparent samples in biology and medicine [32–35]. The method enhances contrast by employing an oblique illumination geometry that prevents unscattered light from entering the objective aperture. As a result, only the light scattered by the specimen contributes to the image, producing a bright signal on a dark background. DF microscopy requires a high-numerical aperture (NA) condenser, as the NA of the imaging objective must be smaller than the minimal NA of the DF condenser. This is illustrated schematically in Fig. 1(a), where the minimum NA of the condenser is determined by α_{\min} . The condition for DF microscopy can therefore be given as $\text{NA}_{\min,\text{condenser}} = \sin \alpha_{\min} > \text{NA}_{\min,\text{objective}}$. A DF condenser has two components, an annular absorbing or reflective aperture and the high-NA illumination lens. Work on absorptive photoresists has previously been reported in [3,4,36] but has never been utilized as part of non-imaging optics.

In this work, we realize the DF condenser by printing structures on both sides of a glass substrate. We 3D-print an annular aperture on one side of the glass substrate and the focusing lens of the condenser on the other side. The annular aperture is printed with the highly absorptive photoresist IP-Superblack [36] using the Nanoscribe Photonic Professional GT (Nanoscribe GmbH & Co. KG). After polymerization, the aperture is developed in a bath of mr-Dev 600 (micro resist technology GmbH) for 2.5 minutes and rinsed with isopropyl alcohol (IPA) for 2 minutes. To print the lens on the backside, we place the glass substrate with the fully developed aperture in the Nanoscribe Quantum X (Nanoscribe GmbH & Co. KG). Then, the aspheric condenser lens is printed with the Nanoscribe IPX-Clear photoresist (Nanoscribe GmbH & Co. KG) and also developed with mr-Dev 600 and IPA, for 20 and 2 minutes, respectively. With both structures printed and developed, the condenser can be illuminated with collimated light. The printed annular aperture blocks the central light rays and allows only a ring of light

Fig. 1. (a) Schematic cross-section of the designed 3D-printed DF condenser and its ray-optical beam path. The condenser consists of a ring-aperture printed with the absorptive photoresist IP-Superblack on one side of a glass substrate and an aspheric lens 3D-printed with IPX-Clear on the other side of the substrate. The condenser is illuminated with collimated light. The 3D-printed absorbing aperture only allows a ring of light to be transmitted onto the printed lens which then focuses the light. The zoom-in of the apex illustrates how the light is focused with a maximum angle α_{max} and a minimum angle α_{min} thus resulting in a maximum and minimum NA of the entire condenser. (b) Microscope image of the aperture printed with IP-Superblack. (c) Microscope image of the lens printed with IPX-Clear. The designed focal length of the lens is 1800 μm . Microscope images with a Keyence VHX-6000. (d) Transmission through a 10 μm thick slab of IP-Superblack on a glass substrate. The jump at 1050 nm is due to switching of the detector in the spectrometer (Cary 7000 Universal Measurement Spectrophotometer, Agilent Technologies Deutschland GmbH).

to reach the lens on the other side. This focused ring of light leads to the desired oblique illumination necessary for DF imaging. By placing a sample in the focus of this illumination and using an imaging objective to collect the light scattered by the sample, we achieve a miniaturized transmission DF condenser. This principle is schematically illustrated in Fig. 1(a). Microscope images of the printed structures are depicted in Figs. 1(b) and 1(c) (see Section 1 of Supplement 1 for additional images at different magnifications). Fabrication with the highly absorptive IP-Superblack photoresist enables the 3D-printed annular aperture to function effectively as a light-blocking element. We characterize the transmission spectrum of the IP-Superblack for a 10 μm thick slab on a glass substrate, which is plotted in Fig. 1(d). The annular aperture also has the height of 10 μm . The transmission remains below 0.4% throughout the entire measured spectral range from 400 nm to 2500 nm, and even lower for the visible spectrum from 400 nm to 780 nm, where it remains at or below 0.2%. This extremely high absorption of the 10 μm thick aperture, especially throughout the visible spectrum, makes it ideal for spatial filtering. This can also be applied in other research fields, such as laser mode shaping, confocal microscopy, or general Fourier optics [37–39]. The designed dimensions of the annular aperture are 1510 μm and 1775 μm , for

the inner and outer diameter of the annular aperture, as well as an outer diameter of 5500 μm for the outer blocking region. The lens of the condenser has a diameter and focal length of 1800 μm leading to an NA of 0.45. Together with the designed sizes of the 3D-printed aperture, this results in a maximum NA_{max} of 0.44 and a minimum NA_{min} of 0.39 for the entire condenser. Therefore, we need to restrict the NA of the imaging objective (20 \times Mitutoyo Plan-Apo Objective, NA 0.42) to values below NA_{min} with an iris, to satisfy the condition for DF microscopy described above. The NA of such a 3D-printed condenser could be increased by multiple designs or by including diffractive surfaces [11,12]. For a performance comparison with a more conventional method of aperture fabrication, we manufacture a second DF condenser with the same design but replace the 2PP 3D-printed aperture with a 100 nm thick chromium aperture fabricated via direct UV writing with the MicroWriter ML3 (Durham Magneto Optics Ltd.). We demonstrate DF imaging using the 3D-printed DF condenser in a setup inspired by [11] with several different samples (see Section 2 of Supplement 1 for details on the setup). We first illuminate and image groups 6 and 7 of an USAF 1951 test chart and compare the performance to the chromium aperture condenser. Resulting DF images of the test chart groups with both condenser types are de-

Fig. 2. Image comparison of positive USAF 1951 test charts illuminated (a), (d) with the IP-Superblack aperture condenser, (b), (e) with the chromium aperture condenser, and (c), (f) with no condenser. (a)–(c) Group 6 and (d)–(f) group 7 of the USAF 1951 test chart.

pictured in Fig. 2, together with corresponding bright-field (BF) images resulting from collimated illumination when no condenser is used in the imaging setup. Figures 2(a) and 2(d) clearly illustrate the DF imaging capabilities of the 3D-printed DF condenser. While the BF images, Figs. 2(c) and 2(f) exhibit a bright background with dark structures, the DF images Figs. 2(a) and 2(d) obtained with the 3D-printed DF condenser show a completely dark background with bright structures. Specifically, the edges of the structure appear bright, while the bulk remains dark, showcasing edge enhancement typical for DF microscopy (see Section 3 of Supplement 1 for a quantitative comparison to commercial condensers). In comparison, the DF images, Figs. 2(b) and 2(e) obtained with the chromium aperture condenser display a much brighter background. The structure edges illuminated with the chromium condenser indicate a brightness similar to the ones illuminated with the IP-Superblack condenser. However, the contrast is strongly reduced by background light. This can likely be attributed to the high reflectivity of chromium, instead of light absorption, highlighting the excellent performance of the IP-Superblack condenser.

For characterization of the contrast enhancement capabilities of the printed DF condenser, we additionally perform imaging on a sample with gold disks on the nanoscale. We fabricate the nanodisk sample on a glass substrate by writing a mask with an electron-beam lithography system (RAITH eLINE Plus) using two PMMA resist layers (200 K and 950 K), followed by depositing gold onto the patterned resist with the electron-beam evaporation system PLS 500 (Pfeiffer Vacuum GmbH). Between the glass substrate and the gold, we use a thin chromium adhesion layer. The gold disks are evaporated on top of the chromium with a height of 30 nm and varying diameters. The obtained DF images are compared to the respective BF images in Fig. 3. A strong visibility increase of the

Fig. 3. DF and BF images of gold nanodisk structures, imaged with and without the IP-Superblack DF condenser. Lissajou pattern made of 150 gold disks with diameters of 300 nm under (a) DF and (b) BF illumination. Spiral made of 24 gold disks with diameters of 250 nm under (c) DF and (d) BF illumination.

nanoscale structures is achieved by the contrast enhancement of the 3D-printed DF condenser, seen in the direct comparison of the left DF- and right BF-images. The images in the top row display the comparison of a Lissajou pattern consisting of 150 gold disks with a diameter of 300 nm. The pattern is only slightly discernible in the BF image Fig. 3(b), which was obtained with collimated illumination. When illuminated with the 3D-printed DF condenser in Fig. 3(a), the pattern is clearly visible, as the individual gold disks appear with a high contrast on the dark background. The difference in obtained BF and DF images becomes more evident when smaller disk diameters are chosen. To showcase this, we additionally image a spiral structure made up of 24 gold disks with a diameter of 250 nm. Due to the smaller disk diameters and increased spacing between the individual disks, the structure is not visible under collimated BF illumination, as observed in Fig. 3(d). Under DF-illumination with the IP-Superblack condenser, every gold disk of the spiral, as depicted in Fig. 3(c), is clearly visible as a bright spot with a dark background. Achieving such high contrast enhancements despite the large distances between the individual disks indicates the ability to image single, individual structures with sizes of 250 nm and below, when using the 3D-printed DF condenser (see Section 4 of Supplement 1 for a comparison to commercial condensers and Section 5 for a quantitative intensity comparison). Theoretically, there is no lower size detection limit for our presented micro-optical system for unlimited illumination times. However, noise from the camera, stray light, and the very low, but non-zero transmission of the IP-Superblack aperture of our miniaturized 3D printed condenser stop us from detecting even smaller gold disks in the current configuration. Still, the presented system illustrates a pathway for a miniaturized DF-system that detects nano-particles used in biosensing, molecular imaging, and sensing of live cells [26–31].

Fig. 4. Unstained onion cells under (a) DF and (b) BF illumination by the 3D-printed DF condenser with the IP-Superblack aperture and collimated light, respectively.

Demonstrating the possibility of performing DF imaging on biological samples, we image unstained onion cells with the 3D-printed DF condenser and compare it to collimated BF illumination in Fig. 4. With the imaging objectives magnification of 20 \times , multiple onion cells can be seen individually. The cells are divided by the cell walls, which are clearly discernible. Inside the cells, the nuclei are visible as a large dot. The BF image displayed in Fig. 4(b) depicts these nuclei, observable as faint dark spots in the bright appearing cells. With a low contrast to the rest of the cell, the visibility of the nuclei is not very high. The contrast between the cell walls and the cells themselves is also relatively low, but their distinction is better than that of the nuclei. This appearance of onion cells is drastically affected when illuminated with the 3D-printed DF condenser. The characteristic edge enhancement of DF imaging is clearly observed in Fig. 4(a). The bulk of the cells now appear dark while the cell walls are bright. The nuclei of the cells in this image appear as large, bright spots with a pronounced contrast to the dark bulk of the cells as the background, highlighting the visibility for biological samples in DF images. Here, we simply used onions to demonstrate the possibility of using our presented method for DF imaging of different biological or medical specimens with a significant edge enhancement and visibility change to conventional BF imaging techniques. This could prove useful for medical applications, such as the detection of different pathogens in the form of viruses or bacteria [33,35] or be applied to imaging of cancer cells or biomarkers [32,34]. Using the two-sided printing method [36], the condenser could be printed semi-monolithically without coordinate realignment. High fabrication throughput of DF condensers could be achieved using nickel tooling manufactured by electroplating 3D-printed masters and subsequent injection molding [40].

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Data availability. Data underlying the results presented in this paper are not publicly available at this time but may be obtained from the authors upon reasonable request.

Supplemental document. See Supplement 1 for supporting content.

REFERENCES

1. M. Malinauskas, M. Farsari, A. Piskarskas, *et al.*, *Phys. Rep.* **533**, 1 (2013).
2. A. Selimis, V. Mironov, and M. Farsari, *Microelectron. Eng.* **132**, 83 (2015).
3. M. D. Schmid, A. Toulouse, S. Thiele, *et al.*, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **33**, 2211159 (2023).
4. P. N. S. Nair, C. Pan, H. Wang, *et al.*, *Light. Adv. Manuf.* **4**, 243 (2023).
5. E. Skliutas, G. Merkininkaitė, S. Maruo, *et al.*, *Nat. Rev. Methods Primers* **5**, 15 (2025).
6. O. M. Young, X. Xu, S. Sarker, *et al.*, *Lab Chip* **24**, 2371 (2024).
7. A. Calikoglu, F. Lux, Y. Taege, *et al.*, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **34**, 2408867 (2024).
8. T. N. Eren, J. Liang, J. L. G. Schneider, *et al.*, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **36**, e02876 (2026).
9. D. Gonzalez-Hernandez, S. Varapnickas, A. Bertocini, *et al.*, *Adv. Opt. Mater.* **11**, 2201701 (2023).
10. H. Wang, W. Zhang, D. Ladika, *et al.*, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **33**, 2214211 (2023).
11. L. Siegle, S. Ristok, and H. Giessen, *Opt. Express* **31**, 4179 (2023).
12. L. Siegle, D. Xie, C. A. Richards, *et al.*, *Opt. Express* **32**, 35678 (2024).
13. J. Weinacker, B. K. Bhandari, A. Viejo Rodriguez, *et al.*, *Adv. Mater. Technol.* **10**, 2401876 (2025).
14. A. Harnik, G. Merkininkaitė, D. Ladika, *et al.*, *Adv. Opt. Mater.* **13**, 2500316 (2025).
15. A. Toulouse, J. Drozella, S. Thiele, *et al.*, *Light Adv. Manuf.* **2**, 20 (2021).
16. T. Li, P. Zhao, P. Wang, *et al.*, *Photoacoustics* **46**, 100784 (2025).
17. S. Angstenberger, P. Ruchka, M. Hentschel, *et al.*, *Opt. Lett.* **48**, 6549 (2023).
18. N. Vaidya and O. Solgaard, *Microsyst. Nanoeng.* **4**, 18 (2018).
19. J. Christopher, L. M. Rooney, M. Donnachie, *et al.*, *Biomed. Opt. Express* **15**, 2224 (2024).
20. D. Zhu, J. Zhang, Q. Xu, *et al.*, *J. Manuf. Process* **116**, 40 (2024).
21. L. M. Rooney, J. Christopher, B. Watson, *et al.*, *Adv. Mater. Technol.* **9**, 2400043 (2024).
22. J. Christopher, R. Craig, R. E. McHugh, *et al.*, *J. Microsc.* **298**, 274 (2025).
23. J. Li, S. Thiele, R. W. Kirk, *et al.*, *Small* **18**, e2107032 (2022).
24. P. Ruchka, A. Kushwaha, J. A. Marathe, *et al.*, *Adv. Photonics* **7**, 026003 (2025).
25. S. H. Gage, *Trans. Am. Microsc. Soc.* **39**, 95 (1920).
26. P. F. Gao, G. Lei, and C. Z. Huang, *Anal. Chem.* **93**, 4707 (2021).
27. A. Wax and K. Sokolov, *Laser Photonics Rev.* **3**, 146 (2009).
28. A. Weigel, A. Sebesta, and P. Kukura, *ACS Photonics* **1**, 848 (2014).
29. T. Li, X. Wu, F. Liu, *et al.*, *Analyst* **142**, 248 (2017).
30. F. Qi, Y. Han, Z. Ye, *et al.*, *Anal. Chem.* **90**, 11146 (2018).
31. B. P. Markhali, M. Sriram, D. T. Bennett, *et al.*, *Biosens. Bioelectron.* **169**, 112612 (2020).
32. W. Qian, X. Huang, B. Kang, *et al.*, *J. Biomed. Opt.* **15**, 046025 (2010).
33. S. Enoki, R. Iino, N. Morone, *et al.*, *Plos ONE* **7**, e49208 (2012).
34. C. Poon, L. Wei, Y. Xu, *et al.*, *Anal. Chem.* **88**, 8849 (2016).
35. M. Imai, K. Mine, H. Tomonari, *et al.*, *Anal. Chem.* **91**, 12352 (2019).
36. M. Schmid, S. Thiele, A. Herkommer, *et al.*, *Opt. Lett.* **48**, 131 (2023).
37. T. Wilson, R. Juskaitis, M. A. A. Neil, *et al.*, *Opt. Lett.* **21**, 1879 (1996).
38. F. Chen, G. Singh, and J. M. Daughton, *J. Appl. Phys.* **93**, 5871 (2003).
39. I. Sizova, T. Moskalev, and L. Mikheev, *Appl. Opt.* **58**, 4905 (2019).
40. S. Wagner, L. Siegle, S. Haeusler, *et al.*, *Adv. Opt. Mater.* **13**, e02089 (2025).